

Study of Effects of Time Interval between Onset of Symptoms and Surgical Intervention on Outcomes in Emergency Abdominal Surgical ConditionsNiraj Kumar¹, Robbins Kumar², Divya Sudarshan³¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Hospital, New Delhi, India²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Hospital, New Delhi, India³PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College and LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

Background: Timely surgical intervention in emergency abdominal conditions is critical for reducing morbidity and mortality. Delays in surgery can exacerbate complications and worsen patient outcomes, making it essential to understand the impact of time intervals between symptom onset and surgical procedures. This study aims to evaluate the effects of the time interval between the onset of symptoms and surgical intervention on patient outcomes in emergency abdominal surgery.

Methods: Eighty patients who required emergency abdominal surgery were included. Data on demographic characteristics, clinical presentation, laboratory findings, time from symptom onset to surgery, length of hospital stay, post-operative complications, and outcomes were collected and analyzed. Statistical analysis included correlation tests and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 46.8 ± 15.3 years, with 72.50% being male. The mean time from symptom onset to surgery was 56.58 ± 30.31 hours. The average hospital stay was 11.31 ± 4.88 days. Post-operative complications were observed in 40% of patients, with surgical site infections being the most common (23.75%). A significant positive correlation was found between the length of hospital stay and time from symptoms to surgery (correlation coefficient: 0.308, p-value: 0.009). The ROC analysis indicated that delays beyond 48 hours significantly increased the risk of complications and mortality (AUC: 0.798).

Conclusion: Delays in surgical intervention beyond 48 hours from symptom onset are associated with increased morbidity and mortality in emergency abdominal surgery. Prompt surgical intervention is crucial to improve patient outcomes.

Recommendations: Implement standardized protocols for rapid diagnosis and surgical intervention in emergency abdominal cases. Enhance resource allocation and management to reduce in-hospital delays, especially in resource-limited settings. Conduct further research to develop global standards for the timing of emergency surgeries.

Keywords: Emergency Abdominal Surgery, Surgical Delay, Patient Outcomes, Time-To-Surgery, Post-Operative Complications.

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Introduction

Emergency abdominal surgery is a critical intervention that can significantly influence patient outcomes depending on the timing of the procedure. Timely surgical intervention is paramount, especially in emergency conditions, where delays can exacerbate complications and increase mortality rates. Recent studies have increasingly focused on understanding the impact of the time interval between symptom onset and surgical intervention to optimize patient outcomes and develop standardized treatment protocols.

The urgency of emergency abdominal surgery arises from the complex and often rapidly deteriorating nature of conditions such as

gastrointestinal perforations, acute appendicitis, and bowel obstructions. A systematic review and network meta-analysis highlighted that delays beyond 48 hours from symptom onset to surgical intervention are associated with higher rates of complications, including perforation and post-operative infections [1]. This finding underscores the critical need for prompt diagnosis and surgical management to mitigate adverse outcomes.

A study published in the BMC Surgery journal examined the relationship between wait times for emergency abdominal surgery and mortality rates. The research found that patients who experienced shorter wait times for surgery had significantly

lower mortality rates compared to those who faced delays. Specifically, a waiting period extending beyond 16 hours was associated with an increased risk of mortality, emphasizing the importance of timely surgical intervention in emergency settings [2].

Furthermore, the World Society of Emergency Surgery (WSES) has proposed a classification system for the timing of acute care surgery, emphasizing the need for surgery within specific time frames based on the severity and progression of the disease. For instance, immediate surgery is recommended for life-threatening conditions such as active intra-abdominal bleeding, while surgery within 6 to 12 hours is suggested for less critical but still urgent cases like localized peritonitis [3]. This classification aids in triaging patients effectively and ensuring that those in critical condition receive the necessary surgical intervention without undue delay.

Recent evidence also highlights the challenges faced in different healthcare settings. Studies have shown that in developed countries, surgical delays are often minimized due to advanced diagnostic tools and better resuscitation facilities. In contrast, developing countries face more significant challenges due to limited resources, resulting in longer wait times and subsequently poorer outcomes [4]. This disparity calls for targeted interventions and resource allocation to improve surgical care in resource-limited settings.

This study aims to evaluate the effects of the time interval between the onset of symptoms and surgical intervention on patient outcomes in emergency abdominal surgery.

Methodology

Study Design: This was a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Deen Dayal Upadhyay hospital New Delhi and MGM Kishanganj, Bihar. The study took place between June 2022 to June 2024.

Study Population: The study followed 80 patients who presented with acute abdomen symptoms.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients >18 years presenting within the study period requiring emergency abdominal surgery.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients lost to follow-up.
- Patients undergoing interventional radiology.
- Patients < 18 years of age.

Sampling Technique: Consecutive sampling was done after applying the relevant inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Data Collection Methods: A cohort of patients was collected prospectively in the Emergency General Surgery database. After applying the inclusion/exclusion criteria, the enrolled patients were explained about the study, and written informed consent was obtained from them.

Detailed socio-demographic information regarding age and gender was collected from all patients based on a pre-designed data sheet and findings of relevant clinical examinations. During clinical examination, height, weight, and BMI were measured. The chief complaints, vitals, and abdominal signs were recorded. Comorbid conditions such as diabetes mellitus, anemia, liver disease, pulmonary Koch's, and obesity were assessed. Laboratory investigations included leukocytosis, serum creatinine, and liver function tests.

Methodology

During the study period, surgical care was provided by a team of general surgeons and residents with fully functional operating rooms staffed by anesthesiologists and anesthesiologist residents. Data collection included basic demographics, presentation history, clinical characteristics, admission diagnosis, surgical interventions, and outcomes. The database was maintained and updated with oversight from faculty. Time to surgery was defined as the time from onset of symptoms to operating room entry.

Medical Records Review

Factors such as gender, age, time of symptom onset, hospital presentation time, operation start time, surgical findings, postoperative complications, and length of hospital stay were reviewed. The primary outcome was the result of the operation based on surgical findings. Postoperative outcomes such as ileus, length of hospitalization, wound complications, intraperitoneal abscesses, and postoperative respiratory complications were analyzed. Time to surgery was statistically correlated with surgical outcomes. Optimum time for surgical intervention in emergency abdominal surgery was determined using this data. Follow-up was done until the patients were discharged and at 30 days post-op.

Outcome Measures

Primary

- Duration from symptoms to surgery.
- Length of stay.
- Postoperative complications.
- Mortality.

Secondary

- Cut-off time to surgery to decrease mortality and complications.

Statistical Analysis: The presentation of categorical variables was done in numbers and percentages (%). Quantitative data were presented as means $\pm$ SD and as median with 25th and 75th percentiles (interquartile range). Data normality was checked using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Non-parametric tests were used for data that were not normally distributed. Data entry was done in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS software (ver 21.0). A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee prior to the start of the study. Written informed consent was taken from all study participants. Confidentiality and privacy were ensured at all stages.

Result

A prospective observational study was conducted, involving 80 patients who required emergency abdominal surgery. The study aimed to evaluate the effects of the time interval between the onset of symptoms and surgical intervention on patient outcomes.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Male	58	72.50%
Female	22	27.50%

Regarding demographic characteristics, the mean age of the study subjects was 46.8 ± 15.3 years. Among the participants, 72.50% were males and 27.50% were females. The chief complaints presented by the patients included pain (98.75%),

vomiting (50.00%), fever (38.75%), and constipation (32.50%). Some patients also reported swelling over the right inguinal region (3.75%) and left inguinal region (1.25%).

Table 2: Chief Complaints

Complaint	Frequency	Percentage
Pain	79	98.75%
Vomiting	40	50.00%
Fever	31	38.75%
Constipation	26	32.50%
Swelling over Right Inguinal Region	3	3.75%
Swelling over Left Inguinal Region	1	1.25%

Abdominal signs observed during the study indicated that 93.75% of patients exhibited guarding, while 16.25% showed distension. In terms of laboratory investigations, 73.75% of patients had leukocytosis with cell counts exceeding 12000 cells/mm³, and 92.50% had serum creatinine levels below 1.5 mg/dL. Most patients (86.25%) had normal liver function test parameters, whereas 13.75% had abnormal results.

The time from symptom onset to surgery was a critical variable in this study. The mean duration was 56.58 ± 30.31 hours, with a median of 48 hours (25th-75th percentile: 24-72 hours). The length of hospital stay for the patients also varied, with a mean stay of 11.31 ± 4.88 days and a median of 10 days (25th-75th percentile: 9.25-14 days). The majority of patients (55.71%) had a hospital stay of 10-15 days.

Table 3: Distribution of Post-operative Complications

Post-operative Complications	Frequency	Percentage
No	48	60.00%
Yes	32	40.00%

Table 4: Comparison of Median Duration from Symptoms to Surgery (in hours) with Post-operative Complications

Post-operative Complications	Duration from Symptoms to Surgery (in hours)	
	No	Yes
Mean $\pm$ SD	43.46 $\pm$ 27.05	76.25 $\pm$ 23.78
Median (25th-75th percentile)	48 (24-72)	72 (72-96)
Range	3-96	16-96

Table 5: Post-operative Outcomes

Post-operative Outcomes	Duration from Symptoms to Surgery (in hours)	
	Died	Discharged
Mean ± SD	84 ± 16.97	52.66 ± 29.83
Median (25th-75th percentile)	96 (72-96)	48 (24-72)
Range	48-96	3-96
P value	0.002	<0.0001

Post-operative complications were observed in 40.00% of the patients, while 60.00% experienced no complications. The most common complications included surgical site infections (23.75%), SIRS with sepsis (11.25%), multi-organ dysfunction

syndrome (10.00%), anastomosis leakage (3.75%), and ventilator-associated pneumonia (2.50%). Despite the complications, 87.50% of patients were discharged, while 12.50% succumbed to their conditions.

Table 6: Receiver operating characteristic curve of duration from symptoms to surgery (in hours) to predict post-operative complications.

Post-operative complications	Duration from symptoms to surgery (in hours)
Area under the ROC curve (AUC)	0.782
Standard Error	0.0531
95% Confidence interval	0.675 to 0.866
P value	<0.0001
Cut off	>48
Sensitivity (95% CI)	80.65% (62.5 - 92.5%)
Specificity (95% CI)	71.43% (56.7 - 83.4%)
PPV (95% CI)	64.1% (47.2 - 78.8%)
NPV (95% CI)	85.4% (70.8 - 94.4%)
Diagnostic accuracy	75.00%

Statistical analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between the length of stay and the time from symptoms to surgery (correlation coefficient: 0.308, p-value: 0.009). The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis for predicting mortality showed an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.798, with a sensitivity of 90.00% and specificity

of 57.14% at a cut-off time of >48 hours. Furthermore, the analysis indicated that patients with post-operative complications had a higher median time from symptoms to surgery (72 vs. 48 hours, p-value <0.001), and mortality was associated with a higher median time (84 vs. 52.66 hours, p-value <0.0001).

Duration from symptoms to surgery(in hours)

Figure 1: Receiver operating characteristic curve of duration from symptoms to surgery (in hours) to predict post-operative complications.

Discussion

The study included 80 patients who required emergency abdominal surgery. The demographic analysis showed that the majority of patients were

middle-aged (mean age: 46.8 years) and predominantly male (72.50%). The most common presenting symptoms were pain (98.75%), vomiting (50.00%), fever (38.75%), and constipation (32.50%). Clinical signs included

guarding (93.75%) and abdominal distension (16.25%). Laboratory findings indicated a high prevalence of leukocytosis (73.75%) and normal serum creatinine levels in most patients (92.50%).

A critical variable in this study was the time from symptom onset to surgery. The average time was approximately 57 hours, with a median of 48 hours. The length of hospital stay averaged 11.31 days, with a median stay of 10 days, highlighting a substantial hospitalization period for these patients. Over half of the patients (55.71%) had a hospital stay between 10 and 15 days.

Post-operative complications were reported in 40% of patients, with surgical site infections being the most common (23.75%). Other significant complications included SIRS with sepsis, multi-organ dysfunction syndrome, anastomosis leakage, and ventilator-associated pneumonia. Despite these complications, a high discharge rate (87.50%) was observed, although 12.50% of patients died.

The statistical analysis revealed a significant correlation between the length of hospital stay and the time from symptom onset to surgery. Patients who experienced delays beyond 48 hours had worse outcomes, including increased post-operative complications and higher mortality rates. The ROC curve analysis indicated that a delay of more than 48 hours was a critical threshold, beyond which the risk of adverse outcomes increased substantially.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of timely surgical intervention in emergency abdominal conditions. Delays in surgery were associated with longer hospital stays, higher rates of post-operative complications, and increased mortality. These findings highlight the need for prompt surgical care within 48 hours of symptom onset to improve patient outcomes in emergency abdominal surgeries. Ensuring rapid diagnosis and reducing in-hospital delays are crucial steps to enhance surgical outcomes and reduce mortality in these patients.

A study evaluated outcomes among patients with acute abdomen and abdominal trauma in Ethiopia. The study found that 35% of patients who underwent surgery more than three days after symptom onset had a mortality rate of 67%. Delays were attributed to prehospital factors, such as initial visits to other health institutions, and in-hospital factors [5].

A systematic review examined the timing of surgical interventions in patients with acute gastrointestinal pathology. The study revealed significant variation in time from admission to surgery (1–72 hours) and associated mortality rates (10.6–74.5%). Delays were linked to imaging, diagnosis, decision-making, and theatre

availability. Early surgery showed reduced mortality rates [6].

A study evaluated the short-term outcomes of patients with perforated peptic ulcer (PPU). The study found that patients presenting within 24 hours of symptom onset had better outcomes, with a mortality rate of 7%. The most common complications were abdominal collection and pleural effusion/pneumonia. Early surgical intervention significantly correlated with shorter hospital stays and reduced complications [7].

The management of acute mesenteric ischemia was studied and found that patients presenting within 24 hours of symptom onset had a 0% mortality rate compared to a 100% mortality rate in those presenting later. Early intervention was crucial in reducing mortality and improving outcomes [8].

A study examined the impact of delayed mobilization on post-discharge outcomes after emergency abdominal surgery in older patients. Delayed mobilization (≥ 36 hours) was associated with a higher risk of 30-day readmission/death, though this association was not statistically significant at 6 months [9].

Conclusion

In summary, the study demonstrated that delays in surgical intervention significantly impact patient outcomes, including the length of hospital stay, post-operative complications, and mortality. Prompt surgical intervention within 48 hours of symptom onset is crucial to improving patient outcomes in emergency abdominal surgical conditions.

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